

Internet of Things-Characteristics and its Applications

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Abstract-The internet of things (IOT) is a computing concept that describes the idea of everyday physical objects being connected to the internet and being able to identify themselves to other devices. With the Internet of Things (IOT) gradually evolving as the subsequent phase of the evolution of the Internet, it becomes crucial to recognize the various potential domains for application of IOT, and the research challenges that are associated with these applications. Ranging from smart cities, to health care, smart agriculture, logistics and retail, to even smart living and smart environments IOT is expected to infiltrate into virtually all aspects of daily life. Even though the current IOT enabling technologies have greatly improved in the recent years, there are still numerous problems that require attention. Since the IOT concept ensues from heterogeneous technologies, many research challenges are bound to arise. The fact that IOT is so expansive and affects practically all areas of our lives, makes it a significant research topic for studies in various related fields such as information technology and computer science. With the former, we have seen an entire ecosystem built around Amazon's Echo devices using the Alexa Voice Service. Google, Microsoft, and Apple have followed suit as well. Since these are independent and closed platforms, the responsibilities of securing the devices rest with the platform providers. In this paper, I highlights characteristics of IOT, Various applications of IOT.

Keywords- IOT, Internet of Things, applications, characteristics smart agriculture, smart cities.

Introduction-

The Internet of Things (IOT) refers to the interconnectivity of physical devices, vehicles, home appliances, and other items embedded with electronics, software, sensors, and connectivity which enables these objects to connect and exchange data. The IOT concept involves extending Internet connectivity beyond traditional devices like desktop and laptop computers, smartphones and tablets to a diverse range of devices and everyday things. The ultimate goal of IOT is to offer advanced connectivity of devices, systems, and services that goes beyond machine-to-machine communications and covers a variety of protocols, domains, and applications.

The recent rapid development of the Internet of Things (IOT) and its ability to offer different types of services have made it the fastest growing technology, with huge impact on social life and business environments. Internet of Things (IOT) devices are rapidly becoming ubiquitous while IOT services are becoming pervasive. Their success has not gone unnoticed and the number of threats and attacks against IOT devices and services are on the increase as well. The Internet of Things (IOT) is an idea that could radically alter our relationship with technology. The promise of a world in which all of the electronic devices around us are part of a single, interconnected network was once a thing of science fiction. But IOT has not only entered the world of nonfiction; it's taking the world by storm. IOT devices are no longer a niche market. They have started to move from our workspaces into our (smart) homes, where IOT devices are expected to have the most significant impact on our daily lives. Most smart home devices will be benign, everyday

appliances like kettles and toasters. Even if these devices are hacked and compromised, short of ruining your breakfast, there's not a lot a hacker can do to cause you grief. The market is currently focusing on the vertical domains of IOT since it is in relatively early phases of development. But IOT cannot be treated as a single thing, or single platform, or even a single technology. The interconnectivity of people, devices and organizations in today's digital world, opens up a whole new playing field of vulnerabilities — access points where the cyber criminals can get in. The overall risk “landscape” of the organization is only a part of a potentially contradictory and opaque universe of actual and potential threats that all too often come from completely unexpected and unforeseen threat actors, which can have an escalating effect. In this paper discussed various security challenges in IOT. The main contribution of this paper is to provide an overview of the applications used in various areas and its characteristics.

Characteristics of Internet of Things (IOT) –

Some most popular characteristics of Internet of things are:

1. Intelligence
2. Connectivity
3. Dynamic Nature
4. Enormous scale
5. Sensing
6. Heterogeneity
7. Security

1. Intelligence- IOT comes with the combination of algorithms and computation, software & hardware that makes it smart. Ambient intelligence in IOT enhances its capabilities

which facilitate the things to respond in an intelligent way to a particular situation and supports them in carrying out specific tasks. In spite of all the popularity of smart technologies, intelligence in IOT is only concerned as means of interaction between devices, while user and device interaction is achieved by standard input methods and graphical user interface. Together algorithms and compute (i.e. software & hardware) provide the “intelligent spark” that makes a product experience smart. Consider Misfit Shine, a fitness tracker, compared to Nest’s intelligent thermostat. The Shine experience distributes compute tasks between a smartphone and the cloud. The Nest thermostat has more compute horsepower for the AI that make them smart.

2. **Connectivity** - Connectivity empowers Internet of Things by bringing together everyday objects. Connectivity of these objects is pivotal because simple object level interactions contribute towards collective intelligence in IOT network. It enables network accessibility and compatibility in the things. With this connectivity, new market opportunities for Internet of things can be created by the networking of smart things and applications. Connectivity in the IOT is more than slapping on a Wi-Fi module and calling it a day. Connectivity enables network accessibility and compatibility. Accessibility is getting on a network while compatibility provides the common ability to consume and produce data. If this sounds familiar, that’s because it is Metcalfe’s Law and it rings true for IOT.
3. **Dynamic Nature** -The primary activity of Internet of Things is to collect data from its environment, this is achieved with the dynamic changes that take place around the devices. The state of these devices change dynamically, example sleeping and waking up, connected and/or disconnected as well as the context of devices including temperature, location and speed. In addition to the state of the device, the number of devices also changes dynamically with a person, place and time. The state of devices change dynamically, e.g., sleeping and waking up, connected and/or disconnected as well as the context of devices including location and speed. Moreover, the number of devices can change dynamically.
4. **Enormous scale** -The number of devices that need to be managed and that communicate with each other will be much larger than the devices connected to the current Internet. The management of data generated from these devices and their interpretation for application purposes becomes more critical. Gartner (2015) confirms the enormous scale of IOT in the estimated report where it stated that 5.5 million new things will get connected every day and 6.4 billion connected things will be in use worldwide in 2016, which is up by 30 percent from 2015. The report also forecasts that the number of connected devices will reach 20.8 billion by 2020. The number of devices that need to be managed and that communicate with each other will be at least an order of magnitude larger than the devices connected to the current Internet. Even more critical will be the management of the data generated and their interpretation for application purposes. This relates to semantics of data, as well as efficient data handling.
5. **Sensing** - IOT wouldn’t be possible without sensors which will detect or measure any changes in the environment to generate data that can report on their status or even interact with the environment. Sensing technologies provide the means to create capabilities that reflect a true awareness of the physical world and the people in it. The sensing information is simply the analogue input from the physical world, but it can provide the rich understanding of our complex world. We tend to take for granted our senses and ability to understand the physical world and people around us. Sensing technologies provide us with the means to create experiences that reflect a true awareness of the physical world and the people in it. This is simply the analog input from the physical world, but it can provide rich understanding of our complex world.
6. **Heterogeneity**-Heterogeneity in Internet of Things as one of the key characteristics. Devices in IOT are based on different hardware platforms and networks and can interact with other devices or service platforms through different networks. IOT architecture should support direct network connectivity between heterogeneous networks. The key design requirements for heterogeneous things and their environments in IOT are scalabilities, modularity, extensibility and interoperability. The devices in the IOT are heterogeneous as based on different hardware platforms and networks. They can interact with other devices or service platforms through different networks.
7. **Security** - IOT devices are naturally vulnerable to security threats. As we gain efficiencies, novel experiences, and other benefits from the IOT, it would be a mistake to forget about security concerns associated with it. There is a high level of transparency and privacy issues

with IOT. It is important to secure the endpoints, the networks, and the data that is transferred across all of it means creating a security paradigm.

Applications of Internet of Things (IOT)

Some useful applications of Internet of Things (IOT) are:

1. Connected Health
2. Smart City
3. Connected Cars
4. Smart Home
5. Smart Farming
6. Smart Retail
7. Smart Supply Chain

1. Connected Health- (Digital Health/Tele health/Telemedicine) IOT has various applications in healthcare, which are from remote monitoring equipment to advance & smart sensors to equipment integration. It has the potential to improve how physicians deliver care and also keep patients safe and healthy. Healthcare IOT can allow patients to spend more time interacting with their doctors by which it can boost patient engagement and satisfaction. From personal fitness sensors to surgical robots, IOT in healthcare brings new tools updated with the latest technology in the ecosystem that helps in developing better healthcare. IOT helps in revolutionizing healthcare and provides pocket-friendly solutions for the patient and healthcare professional. Connected healthcare yet remains the sleeping giant of the Internet of Things applications. The concept of connected healthcare system and smart medical devices bears enormous potential not just for companies, but also for the well-being of people in general. Research shows IOT in healthcare will be massive in coming years. IOT in healthcare is aimed at empowering people to live healthier life by wearing connected devices. The collected data will help in personalized analysis of an individual's health and provide tailor made strategies to combat illness. The video below explains how IOT can revolutionize treatment and medical help.

2. Smart City -Smart city is another powerful application of IOT generating curiosity among world's population. Smart surveillance, smarter energy management systems, automated transportation, water distribution, urban security and environmental monitoring all are examples of internet of things applications for smart cities. IOT will solve major problems faced by the people living in cities like pollution, traffic congestion and shortage of energy supplies etc.

Products like cellular communication enabled Smart Belly trash will send alerts to municipal services when a bin needs to be emptied. By installing sensors and using web applications, citizens can find free available parking slots across the city. Also, the sensors can detect meter tampering issues, general malfunctions and any installation issues in the electricity system.

3. Connected Cars- The automotive digital technology has focused on optimizing vehicles internal functions. But now, this attention is growing towards enhancing the in-car experience. A connected car is a vehicle which is able to optimize its own operation, maintenance as well as comfort of passengers using on board sensors and internet connectivity. Most large auto makers as well as some brave start-ups are working on connected car solutions. Major brands like Tesla, BMW, Apple, and Google are working on bringing the next revolution in automobiles. Connected car technology is a vast and an extensive network of multiple sensors, antennas, embedded software, and technologies that assist in communication to navigate in our complex world. It has the responsibility of making decisions with consistency, accuracy, and speed. It also has to be reliable. These requirements will become even more critical when humans give up entirely the control of the steering wheel and brakes to the autonomous or automated vehicles that are being successfully tested on our highways right now.

4. Smart Home -Smart Home has become the revolutionary ladder of success in the residential spaces and it is predicted Smart homes will become as common as smartphones. Whenever we think of IOT systems, the most important and efficient application that stands out every time is Smart Home ranking as highest IOT application on all channels. The estimated amount of funding for Smart Home startups exceeds \$2.5bn and is ever growing. Wouldn't you love if you could switch on air conditioning before reaching home or switch off lights even after you have left home? Or unlock the doors to friends for temporary access even when you are not at home. Don't be surprised with IOT taking shape companies are building products to make your life simpler and convenient. The cost of owning a house is the biggest expense in a homeowner's life. Smart Home products are promised to save time, energy and money. With Smart home companies like Nest, Ecobee, Ring and August, to name a few, will become

household brands and are planning to deliver a never seen before experience.

5. **Smart Farming** -Smart farming is an often overlooked IOT application. However, because the number of farming operations is usually remote and the large number of livestock that farmers work on, all of this can be monitored by the Internet of Things and can also revolutionize the way farmers work. But this idea is yet to reach a large-scale attention. Nevertheless, it still remains to be one of the IOT applications that should not be underestimated. Smart farming has the potential to become an important application field specifically in the agricultural-product exporting countries.
6. **Smart Retail** -Retailers have started adopting IOT solutions and using IOT embedded systems across a number of applications that improve store operations such as increasing purchases, reducing theft, enabling inventory management, and enhancing the consumer's shopping experience. Through IOT physical retailers can compete against online challengers more strongly. They can regain their lost market share and attract consumers into the store, thus making it easier for them to buy more while saving money. The potential of IOT in the retail sector is enormous. IOT provides an opportunity to retailers to connect with the customers to enhance the in-store experience. Smartphones will be the way for retailers to remain connected with their consumers even out of store. Interacting through Smartphones and using Beacon technology can help retailers serve their consumers better. They can also track consumer's path through a store and improve store layout and place premium products in high traffic areas.
7. **Smart Supply** -Chain Supply chains have already been getting smarter for a couple of years. Offering solutions to problems like tracking of goods while they are on the road or in transit, or helping suppliers exchange inventory information are some of the popular offerings. With an IOT enabled system, factory equipment that contains embedded sensors communicate data about different parameters such as pressure, temperature, and utilization of the machine. The IOT system can also process workflow and change equipment settings to optimize performance [21].

Conclusion- Current state of research in IOT is mainly concentrated on authentication and access control protocols, but with the rapid growth of technology it is essential to consolidate new networking protocols like IPv6 and 5G to achieve

the progressive mash up of IOT topology. The IOT can best be described as a CAS (Complex Adaptive System) that will continue to evolve hence requiring new and innovative forms of software engineering, systems engineering, project management, as well as numerous other disciplines to develop it further and manage it the coming years. The application areas of IOT are quite diverse to enable it to serve different users, who in turn have different needs. The technology serves three categories of users, individuals, the society or communities and institutions. As discussed in the application section of this research paper, the IOT has without a doubt a massive capability to be a tremendously transformative force, which will, and to some extent does already, positively impact millions of lives worldwide. The main emphasis of this chapter was to highlight different applications of IOT are discussed Also discussed characteristics of IOT.

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